

Core concepts and issues in research ethics and integrity, climate ethics, and environmental ethics, in the context of research and innovation: a scoping review protocol

Introduction

Technological innovation is a major driver of environmental degradation, as illustrated by the pollution caused by agricultural pesticides, ozone layer depletion caused by chlorofluorocarbons (CFC), greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions caused by the use of fossil fuels and deforestation, and the radioactive waste of nuclear power plants. At the same time, environmental and climate technologies such as renewable energy technologies, which allow the use of energy sources like solar, wind, water, biomass and geothermal heat, can contribute to reducing the environmental impact of economic activities. The relationship between research and innovation and environmental change is therefore a complex one, especially since technological innovations have the potential to advance one environmental goal at the expense of another. This is the case, for instance, when a technology promises climate benefits but may have harmful impacts on biodiversity, may infringe upon human rights or exacerbate inequalities, particularly with respect to vulnerable populations.

This complexity, and the backdrop of the environmental and climate crises, make it clear that the environment needs to become a subject of concern in research ethics frameworks. Historically, research ethics guidelines have primarily been developed in the field of biomedical research with the aim of protecting individual human participants. They have been extended to cover the interests of participants in social sciences research and the protection of animals. However, it remains difficult for research ethics frameworks to account for impacts on the climate or biodiversity over short, medium, and longer timescales. It is therefore challenging to integrate the findings of environmental and climate ethics into research ethics, given their different methodological and value assumptions.

This scoping review will identify crosscutting concepts and issues within environmental ethics and integrity, climate ethics, and research ethics, in the context of research and innovation. It reflects the fact of pluralism among environmental values and worldviews (Pascual et al. 2023), as well as conceptual pluralism in ethical concepts and issues within climate ethics and environmental ethics. We will map similarities and gaps in this literature and in literature on research ethics and integrity, as well as concepts and issues in wider sustainability science literatures with implications for research and innovation.

As such, this scoping review will seek to answer the research question:

What are the cross-cutting concepts and issues in environmental ethics, climate ethics, and research ethics and integrity, and what are their implications for research, technology and innovation?

Specific objectives are to:

- Map the conceptual overlaps between environmental ethics, climate ethics, and research ethics and integrity.
- Map synergies and tensions between concepts in environmental ethics and climate ethics, including non-Western approaches.

- Map overlaps and gaps between implementation or operationalization of concepts within guidelines, norms and principles, including the EU's 'Do No Significant Harm' Principle.
- Map the application of these concepts for the topics of research, technology, and innovation.
- Identify ethical issues raised by research, technology and innovation in relation to climate change and other environmental issues.
- Identify key principles or guidelines which should be followed to mitigate these ethical issues in relation to research, technology, and innovation.

Methods

This scoping review will be conducted following best practices for scoping reviews, based upon Arksey and O'Malley 2005. This scoping review method is well-adapted for mapping concepts and how they relate, which is our aim here, along with identifying gaps between different research fields (Peters et al. 2015; Sutton et al. 2019). The first step will include an initial screening of abstracts collected in relevant databases against the inclusion and exclusion criteria, followed by a second step where full text screening and qualitative content analysis will take place to identify relevant concepts, topics, and issues. The results will be reported in narrative form using the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-analysis Protocols extension for Scoping Reviews (PRISMA-ScR) checklist as a guide.

Concept

The review is about mapping the relation between environmental ethics, climate ethics, and research ethics and integrity in the context of research and innovation. A separate intercultural search string has been designed to integrate a plurality of normative perspectives in the literature on the relation between these topics, thereby going beyond a Western-centric approach.

Context

We include all literatures that mention the concepts or issues outlined. There is no restriction on the geographical location of studies, or the research disciplines in which these concepts can be used.

Inclusion Criteria

Languages

We will include literature written in English, French, German, and Spanish, although the search will be performed solely in English at this stage. This means that French, German and Spanish literature with titles and abstracts available in English identified using English language search terms will be included and analyzed (see below, sections: **Search strategy**). English, French and German are among the official and working languages of the EU institutions; these are the three "procedural languages" in which the European Commission conducts its internal business. In addition to this, much of the research in EU research institutions is conducted and published in one of these three languages. Spanish was selected as another EU language and as the second most widely spoken language in the world.

Topics

We are looking for concepts, topics, and issues that are related to or that represent aspects of: environmental ethics, environmental justice, climate ethics, climate justice, research ethics and integrity, sustainability ethics, and environmental risks. These concepts, topics, and issues are only considered in relation to research, innovation and technology.

Types of record

This review will consider all peer-reviewed publications, without a time limitation. This includes peer-reviewed research articles, books, book chapters, and review articles.

Exclusion Criteria

This scoping review will exclude results that:

- Are written in any language that is not English, French, German or Spanish.
- Are not peer-reviewed.
- Do not use any of the following ethical concepts, make unspecified/vague references to ‘ethics’, ‘ethical issues’ and synonymous terms/phrases, or that make irrelevant use of terms:
 - E.g. Generic/vague usage of ‘ethics in research’ or ‘ethical issues in research’ or ‘research integrity’ without application to environmental sustainability or environmental impacts or synonyms; generic/vague usage of ‘ethics’ or ‘justice’ or ‘equity’ or ‘intergenerational justice’ or ‘social justice’ or ‘gender justice’ or ‘business ethics’ unconnected to environmental/climate impacts or environmental sustainability or synonyms; irrelevant/metaphorical usage of search terms with different meanings, e.g. ‘work environment’, ‘business climate’; use of ‘sustainability’ (e.g. corporate sustainability) with no mention of environmental sustainability or synonyms

Search Strategy

The search strategy is designed in partnership with consortium members and the Embedded Information Services (EIS) of the Library, ICT Services and Archive (LISA), a service within the University of Twente, especially the Information Specialists of the Behavioral, Management and Social Sciences (BMS) Faculty. Because of the plurality and complexity of topics covered by the review, multiple versions of the search strings have been discussed to find the formulation that is the most adapted to the objectives of the study. The databases used for the review are *Scopus*, *Web of Science*, and *Philosopher’s Index*. The following search strings have been designed:

Scopus search string:

TITLE-ABS-KEY ((research W/3 ethic*) OR (research W/3 integrity) OR (climate W/3 ethic*) OR (environ* W/3 ethic*) OR (climate W/3 justice) OR (environ* W/3 justice)) AND KEY ((climate OR environ*) AND (technology OR innovation))

Web of Science search string:

TS=((research NEAR/3 ethic*) OR (research NEAR/3 integrity) OR (climate NEAR/3 ethic*) OR (environ* NEAR/3 ethic*) OR (climate NEAR/3 justice) OR (environ* NEAR/3 justice)) AND AK=((climate OR environ*) AND (technology OR innovation))

Philosopher's Index search string:

SU ((research N3 ethic*) OR (research N3 integrity) OR (climate N3 ethic*) OR (environ* N3 ethic*) OR (climate N3 justice) OR (environ* N3 justice)) AND SU ((climate OR environ*) AND (technology OR innovation))

Intercultural search string (Scopus only):

TITLE-ABS-KEY (indigenous OR local) AND (pastoralis* OR herder OR fisher* OR hunt* OR forest* OR agriculture OR livelihood OR nomad OR land* OR river* OR sea OR ocean OR mountains) AND (knowledge OR philosophy) AND (values) AND (nature OR mother AND earth OR biodiversity OR ecosystem) AND KEY ((climate OR environ*) AND (technology OR innovation))

The intercultural search string is based on an IPBES systematic literature review (Athayde et al. 2022) with the addition of keywords relevant for this scoping review.

We will use the online software Covidence for managing imported references, removing duplicates, and managing the screening process. Publications will be first screened on title and abstract against the inclusion and exclusion criteria, with a subset then being selected for full text screening based on elaborated inclusion criteria/exclusion. Each abstract will be assessed by two reviewers and any disagreements regarding inclusion will be discussed in team meetings until consensus is reached.

Assessment of methodological quality

As is standard practice for scoping reviews of qualitative literature in social sciences and humanities, no formal assessment of quality will be included in our scoping review.

Extraction of Results

Various attributes of each publication included for qualitative analysis will be recorded in data extraction files. The data will be extracted in RIS format and saved into reference management software (Zotero). If certain data is unavailable, it will be recorded as such.

All members of the review team will take part in the data extraction process. The deduplicated search results will be distributed among the team, using the program Covidence. At stage 1 (review of abstracts), papers will be distributed for an initial pilot study to validate the inclusion and exclusion criteria. The initial inclusion and exclusion criteria will be modified inductively as necessary in light of the pilot study and will be agreed upon before the start of stage 1. At stage 1, abstracts will be distributed so that two people will independently examine each against the inclusion and exclusion criteria. Coders will exclude literature that does not meet the inclusion criteria, and will add additional labels for concepts, topics or themes to the included literature. This will allow for an inductive mapping of the literature.

The initial data extraction file will contain the following:

1. Language
2. Document type
3. Topics of relevance
4. Author(s)
5. Year of publication
6. Country of origin

7. Research field (e.g. humanities, social science, natural science including engineering, and medical science including biomedicine)

Our search results will be presented in a PRISMA flowchart.

Content analysis

Building on the concepts, topics and themes identified in the stage 1 analysis, an initial Stage 2 (full text screening) pilot study will be performed to develop a second stage coding matrix. This will be based upon substantial use of or engagement with the concepts and themes found at Stage 1. This coding matrix will contain definitions, conceptualisations, and substantial usage of these concepts and themes. At stage 2, papers will be distributed for two people to read and code independently using this matrix, with any disagreements resolved in the same way as stage 1.

Contribution of WP partners

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Expected Outputs

The expected outputs of this study will be: 1) this scoping review protocol; 2) project report (deliverable D1.1); and 3) a peer-reviewed review article (deliverable D1.2).

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This review is funded by Horizon Europe under grant agreement no. 101131706. The review team declares that there are no competing interests.

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